

Traditional Faith, Beliefs and Practices of The Tipra's

Alampik Debbarma

Department of History, Tripura University (A Central University), Tripura

Corresponding E-mail : alampik.history@tripurauniv.ac.in

Tipra people encompasses the five original tribes of Tripura, collectively referred to as 'Pancha Tripura' or Five Tipras. These tribes comprise old Tipra (Tripuri or Debbarma), new Tipra (Tripura), Jamatia, Reang or Bru, and Halam. They exhibit shared characteristics, including speaking the 'Kokborok' language, belonging to the Bodo branch of the Tibeto-Burmese language group, having Indo-Mongoloid origin (Kirata), adhering to the Tipra animist religion and embracing the Tipra culture and history. Despite these commonalities, slight regional variations in languages and cultures may exist among the diverse communities and tribes within the Tipra people. Rooted in animism, the Tripuri philosophy attributes living souls to inanimate objects and natural elements, considering all places as sacred with the presence of either benevolent or malevolent spirits. The paper explores the indigenous faiths, beliefs, and practices of the Tipra people in Tripura. Their religion relies on faith, intuition, and emotion rather than strict reasoning. Central to their beliefs is the omnipresence of a supreme almighty god, 'Mwtal Kotor,' identified over time as 'Subrai.' Symbolic rituals, like Wathop, connect them to deities, emphasizing an invisible relationship between gods and living beings. Despite influences from Hinduism, the Tipra people maintain their pre-Hindu practices, including Ker Mwtai and Kharchi Mwtai. This paper explore on the diverse religious fabric of the Tipra community.

Keywords: Tipra people, Tripura, Traditionalfaith, Beliefs, Rituals.